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WAYS TO FORM PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TECHNOLOGY TEACHERS IN A DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

Annotation: This article analyzes modern approaches, pedagogical and psychological foundations and effective methods for forming professional competence of future technology teachers in a digital educational environment. The article substantiates the importance of developing teachers' skills in the effective use of information and communication technologies, and implementing innovative solutions in education through the modernization of the educational process based on digital technologies. At the same time, methods of directing students to independent and creative thinking using digital resources in preparation for professional activity based on a competent approach are highlighted.

Keywords: digital educational environment, professional competence, digital pedagogy, technological literacy, innovative education, ICT skills.

Introduction.

In today's digital transformation, the radical renewal of the education system, the widespread introduction of information and communication technologies (ICT) and the formation of a digital educational environment create new competency requirements for the teacher. In particular, the formation of digital pedagogical competence in the process of professional training of future teachers in technological disciplines is emerging as one of the urgent scientific and practical problems.

A digital learning environment is a modern learning space that provides interactive cooperation between students and teachers, organized on the basis of multimedia tools, electronic learning resources, cloud technologies, and digital learning platforms. In such an environment, a teacher is required not only to convey the content of the subject, but also to have skills such as digital pedagogical design, information security, digital culture, distance learning management, and the use of artificial intelligence tools in education.

For future technology teachers, professional competence is not only a set of technical knowledge and practical skills, but also a complex ability aimed at integrating modern technological tools into the educational process, using innovative methods, and developing and implementing learning strategies that meet the individual needs of students. This article analyzes the process of developing digital competence in the preparation of future technology teachers for professional activity, its stages, methodological foundations and modern approaches. This study aims to compare national and foreign experiences, identify mechanisms for integrating digital technologies and reveal ways to implement them in practice.

Materials.

The rapid development of the digital educational environment has brought fundamental changes to the modern educational process. These changes, first of all,

directly affect the professional formation of future teachers. Technology teachers, especially as the pedagogical subject closest to ICT tools, are required to master the skills of operating in a digital environment. In this regard, the concept of professional competence occupies a central place. It is not limited only to a set of traditional knowledge and skills, but also includes the ability to effectively use modern digital technologies, software tools, virtual laboratories, and digital educational resources.

The problem being considered as a material is a systematic analysis of existing approaches and pedagogical tools for the formation of professional competence of future technology teachers in a digital educational environment. At the initial stage, future teachers should be formed with initial knowledge of digital literacy, media information culture and Internet safety. At the subsequent stages, deeper competencies such as the use of interactive educational tools, the design of distance learning lessons, the use of digital assessment technologies, and working with platforms based on artificial intelligence are formed. To this end, it is advisable to introduce methodological manuals, simulation programs, educational constructors (for example, Arduino, Tinkercad, Scratch, etc.), digital portfolios and analytical reflection methods on the pedagogical integration of digital technologies in educational institutions. In this regard, the practical application of new pedagogical concepts and terms such as "digital didactics", "digital methodology", "interactive design" serves as an important scientific and theoretical basis for future technology teachers.

Also, in this direction, the use of adaptive learning platforms, taking into account the individual level of mastery of future teachers, and the use of tasks designed based on a constructivist approach in the formation of competencies are of urgent importance. From this perspective, the digital educational environment is not only a set of technological tools, but also a space for multifaceted interactive, reflexive and creative cooperation between the student and the teacher. The formation of digital professional competence of future technology teachers is a complex and continuous process based on modern methodologies, technologies and personalized learning strategies. This material serves as a theoretical basis and practical direction for developing effective solutions in this direction.

Literature analysis (review):

Scientific research on the issue of preparing future technology teachers for professional activity in a digital educational environment has become a relevant topic in recent years at the intersection of pedagogy and digital technologies. At the global and national levels, research on this issue has been conducted in two main areas: the first is the theoretical foundations of the formation of teachers' digital competence, and the second is the methodological approaches and technologies used in educational practice.

Internationally, the research of Livingstone, Selwyn, Mishra and Koehler provides an in-depth analysis of teachers' digital pedagogical preparation based on the "TPACK model" (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge). This model bases the

preparation of a teacher to work effectively in a digital educational environment by integrating their technological, pedagogical and content knowledge. Mishra and Koehler emphasize the importance of developing digital competence based on a contextual, integrated and reflexive approach.

In the national literature, pedagogical scientists such as A. Tokhliyev, M. Ismoilova, A. Nishonova, A. Melikulov have covered the issues of the content of digital education, the use of modern ICT tools, the didactic capabilities of a virtual educational environment and the formation of a digital culture. For example, A. Nishonova's research describes methods for developing teachers' professional competence through the integration of digital technologies in distance learning. At the same time, methodological guides have been developed on teachers' digital literacy and skills in working with modern educational platforms.

Also, the digital competence standards for teachers of UNESCO, OECD and the European Commission are one of the important sources in this area. In particular, the DigCompEdu (European Framework for the Digital Competence of Educators) model offers a system for assessing digital competencies through 6 main components and 22 indicators. Through this approach, the level of use of digital tools, the skills of organizing interactive lessons, and the potential for using digital technologies in assessment are analyzed based on specific criteria.

In conclusion, it can be said that although the existing literature covers important aspects of this topic, there are still aspects that need in-depth analysis, namely in areas such as the use of non-traditional pedagogical technologies, project-based approaches, gamification and artificial intelligence in the formation of digital competence of technology teachers. Therefore, this article serves to fill this gap.

Discussion:

The digitalization of the modern educational process requires not only technical innovation, but also fundamental changes in didactic, methodological and pedagogical approaches. The development of competencies in the process of professional formation of future technology teachers based on seamless integration with the digital learning environment is a complex system that combines innovative strategies in education, technological literacy, digital pedagogy and personalized learning models.

The main attention in the discussion process should be paid to existing problems, opportunities and practical solutions in the formation of digital competence of future teachers. First of all, most technology teachers are accustomed to building their professional activities on the basis of traditional methods and are reluctant to use digital technologies as educational tools. This situation is explained by the insufficient formation of digital pedagogical culture, the lack of methodological guidelines for the use of information and communication technologies, and the fact that the material and technical base in educational institutions in some cases does not meet the requirements.

However, for teachers specializing in teaching technology, digital tools are not just a tool, but a key resource that is directly integrated with the content and methodology

of the lesson. For example, organizing practical classes using Arduino microcontrollers, 3D modeling programs, online laboratories (PhET, Tinkercad), mobile applications not only increases student interest, but also actively develops the digital competence of the teacher.

Also, methods such as educational projects, problem-based assignments, reflective analysis, portfolio management, and peer assessment, developed based on a constructivist approach, are effective tools in preparing future teachers for work in a digital environment. In this process, the teacher acts not only as a provider of knowledge, but also as a facilitator, guide, and mentor. Such a role transformation brings new levels of quality to the teacher's professional competence. Based on the above, it can be said that methodological approaches with a consistent strategy, the ability to use modern technological platforms, as well as the skills to understand and adhere to digital ethics are of paramount importance in the formation of digital competence. Importantly, these competencies directly affect the intellectual and social development of the student's personality. For future technology teachers, the digital educational environment is not just a new environment, but also a necessary tool and environment for their professional growth. The formation of their digital competence should be carried out through systematic, targeted, innovative and person-oriented approaches.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the formation of professional competence of future technology teachers in the digital educational environment is one of the most urgent tasks of the modern education system. This process includes not only the acquisition of technical means, but also the ability to use them in accordance with didactic goals, the effective use of digital resources, the introduction of innovative methods and the formation of students' digital culture. It is necessary to create the necessary conditions for increasing the professional potential of the teacher through digital pedagogical approaches, interactive learning environments, distance learning technologies and media tools.

Also, the formation of digital competence should be carried out gradually and continuously, and in this process, methodological guides, electronic platforms, virtual laboratories and analytical assessment tools should be actively used. The results of this study will serve to adapt future teachers of technology to digital education and ensure their professional growth.

References:

1. Mishra P., Köler M. Technological pedagogical content of knowledge: a framework model for teachers // Teachers College Record. – 2006. – No. 108(6). – P. 1017–1054.
2. Selvin N. Education and digital technologies: a critical view. – M.: Infra-M Publishing House, 2021. – 240 p.
3. Tokhliev A. Information and communication technologies in education. – T.: Science and technology, 2019. – 172 p.

4. Ismailova M. The role of digital technologies in modern education // Journal of Pedagogical Skills. – 2022. – No. 3. – P. 45–50.
5. Melikkulov A. Issues of forming digital literacy in higher education // Journal of Innovative Education. – 2021. – No. 1. – P. 36–41.
6. European Commission. Digital competence of teachers: the European structure of DigCompEdu. – Luxembourg: Publications of the EU, 2017. – 86 p.
7. Nishonova A. Approaches to developing teacher competence in digital education // Uzbekistan Pedagogical Bulletin. – 2023. – No. 2. – P. 58–64.